

2D RZ-Geometry SN-Sweeper in Griffin Without a Special Starting Direction Solve

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ABSTRACT

Griffin is a reactor physics code targeting multiphysics simulations of advanced reactors and includes a sweep solver for SN transport. The sweeper in Griffin worked for Cartesian geometry, but a sweep solver for RZ-geometry needed to be added. This work presents the novel RZ-geometry discretization and sweeping algorithm implemented in Griffin. The main motivation for the implementation described in this work was to enable adapting an existing Cartesian geometry SN sweeper to handle sweeping in RZ-geometry with minimal changes to the existing code base. One significant difference that usually exists between an RZ-geometry sweeping algorithm and a Cartesian geometry sweeper involves the need for a special solve for the so-called “starting direction”. This special starting direction solve does not exist in Cartesian discretization. The novel aspect of this work is that the RZ discretization described here when coupled with the specific solution algorithm allows for an existing unstructured mesh Cartesian geometry sweeper to sweep in cylindrical coordinates in a simpler way, to the authors’ knowledge, than any existing methodology documented in literature.

Keywords: cylindrical coordinates, SN transport, Griffin, RZ-geometry, sweeping

1. INTRODUCTION

Griffin [1] is a reactor physics code that includes PN (spherical harmonics expansion method) and SN (discrete ordinates method) with various finite element methods (FEM) for solving deterministic transport. It was created specifically for modeling advanced reactors and includes specific features for this in addition to general reactor analysis capabilities. For SN transport, Griffin relies on the popular discontinuous finite element (DFEM) discretization and includes the commonly used matrix free algorithm referred to as “sweeping” for solving the SN equation. The sweeper implemented in Griffin for use with Cartesian geometry is described in Ref. [2].

Griffin optionally includes MC²-3 for generating cross sections relevant to analyzing fast spectrum reactors. The workflow to generate fast reactor multigroup cross sections includes the need to create an RZ-geometry model that represents important features of the core. This RZ-geometry model is then used for an ultrafine group transport solve to get a spectrum for use generate cross sections [3]. A sweeper for solving DFEM-SN transport in RZ-geometry needed to be added to Griffin for this purpose.

The novel aspect of this work is that the discretization described here when coupled with the specific solution algorithm allows for an existing unstructured mesh Cartesian geometry sweeper to be adapted to include RZ-geometry in a simpler way than other commonly used methods. The DFEM-SN equations in RZ-geometry have an angular derivative term not present in the Cartesian geometry equations. As explained in more detail in Section 3.1, a special sweep solve is required in most common RZ-geometry discretizations to start the solve. This special solve is for the so called “starting direction”, which is

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not a concept in Cartesian geometry discretizations and this is the most significant difference between sweeping in RZ-geometry and Cartesian geometry.

The RZ-geometry discretization implemented in Griffin avoids the special starting direction solve as described in Section 3.1. It does introduce a different complexity not typically present in other discretizations and the method Griffin uses to sweep the discretized SN-equation is discussed in Section 3.2. As described in that section, the sweeping algorithm in Griffin is very similar between Cartesian geometry and cylindrical geometry, the only real difference being that the angular derivative adds limited coupling between some directions, but this is easy to handle. Dependencies are simply added between directions when determining what order to solve the directions in much like is done when handling reflecting boundary conditions in any coordinate system.

2. TRANSPORT IN CYLINDRICAL COORDINATES

The mono-energetic transport equation is first introduced to provide a basis for subsequent discussion. Griffin uses the multigroup method to treat energy dependence, but the ideas presented in this work are applied to the multigroup equation in the same way as the mono-energetic equation so it is used to make the discussions more clear. The mono-energetic transport equation is shown below

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot (\vec{\Omega}\psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega})) + \sigma_t(\vec{r})\psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) &= \frac{\sigma_s(\vec{r})}{4\pi}\phi(\vec{r}) + \frac{q(\vec{r})}{4\pi} \quad \text{in } \mathcal{H} \notin \partial\mathcal{H}^- \\ \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) &= g(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) \quad \text{on } \partial\mathcal{H}^- \\ \phi(\vec{r}) &= \int_{4\pi} \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) d\Omega, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

defined on domain \mathcal{H} where $\psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega})$ is the angular flux, σ_t is the total cross section, σ_s is the scattering cross section, q is an isotropic volumetric source, ϕ is the scalar flux, and g is a function specified on the portions of the boundary $\partial\mathcal{H}^-$ given by $\vec{n} \cdot \vec{\Omega} < 0$ where \vec{n} is the outward normal for \mathcal{H} .

Cylindrical coordinates are illustrated in Figure 1. The polar angle $\varphi \in [0, \pi]$ is with respect to the fixed z-direction \hat{e}_z at a point in space. The cosine of the polar angle $\mu = \cos(\varphi)$ is typically used in equations instead of the the polar angle itself. $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ is the azimuthal angle. The azimuthal angle ω is measured in the plane of $\hat{e}_r, \hat{e}_\theta$ starting from \hat{e}_r . Thus $\vec{\Omega} = (\Omega_z, \Omega_r, \Omega_\theta)$ with $\Omega_z = \mu$, $\Omega_r = \sqrt{1 - \mu^2} \cos(\omega)$, $\Omega_\theta = \sqrt{1 - \mu^2} \sin(\omega)$.

The transport equation in RZ-geometry is shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Omega_r}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r\psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega})) - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \omega} (\Omega_\theta \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega})) + \Omega_z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) \\ + \sigma_t(\vec{r})\psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) &= \frac{\sigma_s(\vec{r})}{4\pi}\phi(\vec{r}) + \frac{q(\vec{r})}{4\pi}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The most significant difference between this equation and the Cartesian form is the presence of an angular derivative which is discussed further in Section 2.1. Before discussing this equation further, the SN discretization is briefly introduced. The SN equation is formed by first defining an angular quadrature such that $\phi(\vec{r}) = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \psi_i$, where w_i is the quadrature weight for abscissa ψ_i (with N total points) and $\psi_i = \psi(\vec{\Omega}_i, \vec{r})$. The SN transport equation is then

$$\mathbf{L}\psi = \sigma_s \mathbf{P}\psi + \frac{q}{4\pi} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{L} = \{\nabla \cdot \vec{\Omega}_1 + \sigma_t, \dots, \nabla \cdot \vec{\Omega}_M + \sigma_t\}$, $\psi = \{\psi_1(\vec{r}), \dots, \psi_M(\vec{r})\}^T$, and \mathbf{P} is application of the angular quadrature such that $\mathbf{P}\psi = \phi(\vec{r})$. \mathbf{L} is typically referred to as the “streaming plus collision” operator.

Figure 1. Notations used in this work for cylindrical coordinates.

The sweep solver in many cases can invert \mathbf{L} efficiently. There are multiple ways to use a sweeper but a simple method, generally referred to as source iteration, is sufficient to consider for subsequent discussions. This iterative scheme is shown below:

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}^{\ell+1} = \mathbf{L}^{-1} \left[\sigma_s \mathbf{P} \boldsymbol{\psi}^{\ell} + \frac{q}{4\pi} \right] \quad (4)$$

where ℓ is an iteration index. The spatial discretization of the SN equation is not discussed in this work, but as mentioned in the introduction, Griffin uses DFEM for spatial discretization.

2.1. Angular Derivative

The presence of an angular derivative term in the RZ-geometry transport equation is the primary difference compared to the Cartesian geometry equation, which has only spatial derivatives. Before describing how this term is calculated, some details about the angular quadrature must be mentioned first. The method for treating the azimuthal derivative covered in this section is only implemented in Griffin for Gauss–Chebychev quadrature. Figure 2 plots a 2D S12 Gauss–Chebychev quadrature for illustrative purposes showing on a hemisphere the terminal ends of the direction vectors in the quadrature. We use the term S12 to indicate that the number of polar directions and the number of polar directions per octant are both equal to six.

In Figure 2, the directions can clearly be grouped together by their Ω_z or μ components and this grouping is emphasized in the figure by the solid lines passing through points that belong to the same group. As shown, there are six levels with there being 12 in total accounting for the symmetric points not shown with negative Ω_z components. The reason for pointing this feature of the angular quadrature out is that the RZ-geometry transport equation contains only a partial derivative in angle with respect to ω . Since the directions grouped together all have the same Ω_z component, this partial derivative couples all the directions on a level together but adds no coupling between directions on different levels. With this in mind, the following notation for direction indices will be used: $\psi_{m,n}$ will denote the function value for direction n on level m and similarly $w_{m,n}$ will denote the weight.

As explained in detail in Ref. [4], the angular derivative term can be written as

$$\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial \omega} (\Omega_{\theta} \psi(\vec{\Omega})) \right|_{\vec{\Omega}=\vec{\Omega}_{m,n}} = \frac{\gamma_{m,n+1/2} \psi_{m,n+1/2} - \gamma_{m,n-1/2} \psi_{m,n-1/2}}{w_{m,n}} \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Gauss-Chebyshev S12 quadrature set plotted over half the unit sphere. The other half of the directions is not shown, but obvious from symmetry.

with the constraints

$$\gamma_{m,N_m+1/2} = \gamma_{m,1/2} = 0, \quad (6)$$

$$\gamma_{m,n+1/2} = \gamma_{m,n-1/2} + w_{m,n} \zeta_{m,n}, n = 1, \dots, N_m. \quad (7)$$

and ζ is shown in Figure 1. The first constraint is to ensure $\int_0^\pi \frac{\partial}{\partial \omega} [\Omega_\theta \Psi] d\omega = (\gamma_{m,N_m+1/2} \psi_{m,N_m+1/2} - \gamma_{1/2} \psi_{m,1/2}) = 0$ is met for any angular fluxes. The second constraint is to ensure $\frac{\partial}{\partial \omega} (\Omega_\theta) = \zeta$.

A simple diamond difference relationship [4] was commonly used in the past to relate the half index angular fluxes to those at quadrature points, $\psi_{m,n} = 1/2(\psi_{m,n-1/2} + \psi_{m,n+1/2})$. However, Walters and Morel [5] pointed out that the quadrature point $\psi_{m,n}$ does not lie in the middle of the angular cell bounded by $(\psi_{m,n-1/2}, \psi_{m,n+1/2})$ for any popularly used angular quadrature set including Gauss-Chebyshev. Use of diamond differencing was the cause of accuracy issues noted but not fully resolved by other researchers. Walters and Morel [5] showed that using a weighted average was correct and eliminated accuracy issues noted by previous researchers. The weighted average is generally referred to as weighted diamond difference (WDD). The half index angular fluxes are defined using WDD as follows,

$$\psi_{m,n} = \tau_{m,n} \psi_{m,n+1/2} + (1 - \tau_{m,n}) \psi_{m,n-1/2} \quad (8)$$

where the values of $\tau_{m,n}$ are defined by

$$\tau_{m,n} = \frac{\zeta_{m,n} - \zeta_{m,n-1/2}}{\zeta_{m,n+1/2} - \zeta_{m,n-1/2}} \quad (9)$$

The value of $\omega_{m,n+1/2}$ is needed to compute $\xi_{m,n+1/2}$, and this is given by the following where w_m is the sum of all weights $w_{m,n}$ on level m (i.e., $w_m = \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} w_{m,n}$)

$$\omega_{m,n+1/2} = \omega_{m,n-1/2} - \pi \frac{w_{m,n}}{w_m}, \quad (10)$$

with $\omega_{m,1/2} = \pi$.

3. GRIFFIN RZ-GEOMETRY TRANSPORT SWEEPING ALGORITHM

The main topic of this work is avoiding having to use a special starting direction solve when implementing a sweeper for solving RZ-geometry transport. This idea is introduced in the next section.

3.1. Avoiding the Special Starting Direction Solve

The typical way of solving the RZ-geometry transport equation with a special starting direction solve will be briefly explained first. For cylindrical coordinates, each μ_m level shown in Figure 2 has a starting direction, which is $\psi_{m,1/2}$. To see the special condition that exists related to these starting directions, Equation 2 is first rewritten, expanding out the derivatives

$$\Omega_r \frac{\partial \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega})}{\partial r} - \frac{\Omega_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega})}{\partial \omega} + \Omega_z \frac{\partial \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega})}{\partial z} = \frac{\sigma_s(\vec{r})}{4\pi} \phi(\vec{r}) + \frac{q(\vec{r})}{4\pi}. \quad (11)$$

For the starting directions, $\omega = \pi$ and $\Omega_\theta = 0$. Equation 11 is rewritten specifically for the starting direction below

$$\Omega_r \frac{\partial \psi_{m,1/2}}{\partial r} + \Omega_z \frac{\partial \psi_{m,1/2}}{\partial z} = \frac{\sigma_s(\vec{r})}{4\pi} \phi(\vec{r}) + \frac{q(\vec{r})}{4\pi}. \quad (12)$$

This equation has the same form as a 2D Cartesian geometry transport equation and the same sweep solve used for Cartesian geometry can be used to solve for the required starting directions. The typical way to solve the RZ-cylindrical SN equation is to first solve for the starting directions using this special starting direction sweep. Then Equation 8 can be used to replace occurrences of $\psi_{m,1}$ in the SN equation with $\psi_{m,3/2}$, and then the equation can be solve for $\psi_{m,3/2}$. This cell edge angular flux is then used as input data to solve for $\psi_{m,5/2}$ and so on.

Instead of performing a special solve for the starting directions, the solver implemented in Griffin simply uses a linear extrapolation to compute $\psi_{m,1/2}$. This is defined by the following equation where the definitions of a and b will be used in the next section.

$$\psi_{m,1/2} = \frac{\xi_{m,1/2} - \xi_{m,2}}{\xi_{m,1} - \xi_{m,2}} \psi_{m,1} + \frac{\xi_{m,1/2} - \xi_{m,1}}{\xi_{m,2} - \xi_{m,1}} \psi_{m,2} = a\psi_{m,1} + b\psi_{m,2} \quad (13)$$

3.2. Sweeping Algorithm

The idea of sweeping is discussed briefly in the introduction and more information can be found in Ref. [2] and the references in that work, but some ideas are reviewed next. For a two dimensional mesh with all mesh elements being convex, there is some order the elements can be visited such that that the DFEM discretized streaming plus collision operator can be directly inverted and this ordering will be referred to here as the sweep ordering. In the case of the cartesian equations with source iteration, the sweep solve for each direction is independent and the directions can be solved in any order. In the case of RZ-geometry, the angular derivative couples directions together on the same m level, but as described in the previous section, the directions on different m levels can be solved at the same time, and the directions on the same m level are solved sequentially to invert the streaming plus collision operator

with the exception that when the linear extrapolation in Equation 13 is used, the first two directions are coupled together. The method Griffin uses to handle this situation is described in this section.

For a two dimensional mesh that will be used in RZ-geometry with Gauss–Chebychev quadrature, there are only two sweep orderings for each m level depending on whether ω is greater than or less than $\pi/2$. For any quadrature set with more than two directions on each m level, that is greater than S2, the first and second direction which are used in Equation 13 have the same sweep ordering. The special case of S2 will be discussed later. Since the first and second direction have the same sweep ordering when S4 or greater is used, it would be possible to solve these two directions together at the same time followed by solving the remaining directions in the normal way; one at a time. In this way, the streaming plus collision operator would still be inverted. But doing this somewhat invalidates one of the main motivations for avoiding the special starting direction solve which was to have the cylindrical sweeping algorithm be similar to the Cartesian version. Starting the sweep solve on each m level with a coupled solve of the first two directions would be significantly different from how the Cartesian equations are solved and qualitatively not really simpler than implementing a special starting direction solve. Instead, the equations are solved by simply lagging $\psi_{m,2}$ in Equation 13 at the start of a solve on each m level when $\psi_{m,1/2}$ is needed as an inflow boundary condition.

The case of S2 quadrature where there are only two directions on each m level is special. In this case, on an m level, the first direction will be going into the cylinder and the second will be coming out of the cylinder. In this case, the only two directions on each m level have different sweep orderings. Because of this, simply lagging $\psi_{m,2}$ and using the sweeper as described in the previous paragraph does not appear to work for solving the SN equation and Griffin currently throws an error informing a user they need to use S4 or greater. This is not a significant limitation of the methodology since S2 is nearly equivalent to diffusion and there would be no benefit in terms of accuracy to using S2 over simply using a diffusion calculation. However, the S2 system can be solved using a direct solver which may be useful for comparing the S2 solution to diffusion.

3.3. Verification Activities

Several verification activities were performed for the RZ-sweeper implemented in Griffin. Griffin already included a different method for handling the angular derivative which relied on a PN expansion method for handling the numerical derivative as described in Ref [6]. This method so far has not been practical because all directions in an angular quadrature set are coupled together and no effective method for solving the resulting system has been developed. The WDD method implemented as described in this work was compared with the PN based method for several problems. The WDD method converged more quickly with the number of directions for the problems investigated, but both methods appear to converge to the same solution.

The novel RZ-discretization described in this work was also compared with the traditional method that uses a special starting direction solve. Griffin does not include the traditional SN solve algorithm with a starting direction, so another SN code that implements that method, OpenSn [7], was used for the comparison. A test problem in cylindrical coordinates was created for a mono-energetic transport calculation with $\sigma_t = 1$ and $\sigma_s = 0.2$. The length of the cylinder was 10 and two radii were tested; $r=1$ and $r=5$. This investigation had the limited scope of providing some results for this work. Further analysis of the rz-discretization without a starting direction compared to the traditional discretization will be reported in a future work.

The scalar flux solution for this test problem is shown in Figure 3a. A regular mesh of 100x1000 was used, a zoomed in view of the mesh is shown in Figure 3b. For the case with $r=5$, the mesh used was 500x1000. Griffin and OpenSn use a similar spatial discretization. Although not exactly the same, the fine mesh used should cause any differences in spatial discretization error to be much less than angular discretization error. Griffin and OpenSn solutions for total leakage out of the cylinder are shown for $r=1$ and $r=5$ in Figure 4 for different angular quadrature orders. For the specific test problems investigated,

the RZ discretization described in this work converges faster compared to the discretization with a starting direction. Interestingly, the method described in this work appears to have a lower initial error for the $r=1$ case compared to the method with a starting direction while it has higher initial error for the $r=5$ case.

As mentioned in the previous section, the method described in this work for calculating the starting direction couples directions together such that the a sweep solve does not appear to be effective with S2 quadrature, although it works for S4 and greater. However, the linear system for S2 can still be assembled within Griffin and solved directly. It is interesting to note that the method described in this work exactly replicates diffusion for S2, that is the flux is exactly linearly anisotropic. As discussed in detail in Ref. [5], the traditional method of using a slab solve to compute the starting direction does not reproduce diffusion for S2 since the starting direction itself is an additional direction in the addition to those in the S2 quadrature set.

Figure 3. Scalar flux solution for the test cylindrical coordinates problem (a) shown with a zoomed in view of the mesh (b).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The RZ-geometry sweeper implemented in Griffin has been heavily used since first being implemented as part of the workflow for generating fast reactor cross sections. It runs efficiently in parallel; although, given that its main purpose is to be used for smaller RZ-geometry problems, parallel scaling to a large number of processors is not a primary concern. More information related to its parallel scalability will be provided in a future expanded work. The RZ-geometry discretization implemented in Griffin was compared with the traditional discretization as implemented in OpenSn. Future works will expand on this analysis comparing the discretization described in this paper without a starting direction to the traditional discretization with a starting direction.

Figure 4. Comparison of convergence of leakage for a cylinder with radius=1 (a), and radius=5 (b)

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